

Progress in Researching the Ability of Geopolymer Concrete to Withstand a Penetration of Chloride Ions

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Abstract:

Geopolymer concrete is an innovative environmentally friendly construction material, and the transportation of chloride ions plays a crucial role in determining its durability. This study provides a summary of the characteristics and limitations of the test techniques used to measure the resistance of geopolymer concrete to the permeability of chloride ions, based on the introduction of the chloride ion transport mechanism in geopolymer concrete. This text provides an overview of the features and constraints of the test techniques used to assess the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion permeability. It also explores the connections between the mechanism of chloride ion transport and the resistance of

geopolymer concrete to chloride ion permeability. This paper provides a concise overview of the properties and constraints of the test methods used to measure the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion permeability. It also discusses the factors that can affect the chloride ion permeability resistance of geopolymer concrete and presents a comparison between different methods. The article continues by highlighting that the chloride transport model of geopolymer concrete is complex. The essay continues by highlighting the chloride transport model of geopolymer concrete, specifically focusing on the impact of individual parameters such as high temperature, freezing-thaw cycles, and the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion permeability. The study investigates the impact of freeze-thaw cycles, alkali admixture, and water glass modulus on the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride penetration. The infiltration of chloride, as well as the precision of determining the concentration border of chloride ions for colour rendering, require further in-depth investigation.

Keywords: *geopolymer concrete; chloride ion; permeability; transport mechanism; testing technique; influencing factors.*

Introduction

Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) concrete has elevated levels of both raw ingredients and mechanical qualities (Wang, et al., 2020; Parthiban, & Vijayan, 2020). It is a highly utilised construction material in the development of worldwide infrastructure systems. While OPC is carbon-neutral, its manufacture emits a significant quantity of CO₂ into the atmosphere, leading to global warming, acidification, and

eutrophication. However, the production of OPCs produces huge amounts of CO₂ emissions that are aggravating global warming and also socio related as well as environmental issues like acidification Li, (2019) so there is a growing need for construction industries to adopt green building materials on the planet.

In 1978 a new type of green inorganic cementitious material was proposed by Prof. Davidovits (1991), called Geopolymer where the

source material is exclusively composed of Natural Aluminium silicate minerals like Kaolin and montmorillonite.

The green binder is derived from the natural aluminosilicate minerals (e.g. kaolin, montmorillonite and slag for silicon dioxide [SiO₂] and aluminium under different forms) by polymerizing various types of aluminosilicate precursors through a solidification process using an alkaline activator solution combined with water glass as soluble silicates (Davidovits, 1991).

The use of alkalinity high solution and soluble silicate can activate a variety of aluminosilicate precursors copolymerization, to achieve efficient production Lahoti, (2017), Rostami, & Behfarnia, (2017), the CO₂ emissions produced during its manufacturing process is only 1/6 that from silicate cement (Hassan, Arif, & Shariq, 2019). Geopolymer concrete has 91% less carbon emissions in comparison to ordinary cement (Hassan, Arif, & Shariq, 2019), which is a significant reduction in the carbon footprint of geopolymer concretes (GPC) (as shown concerning conventional concrete).

Steel reinforcement corrosion is the main factor leading to concrete structure durability, and carbonation and ion radicals are mainly two promoters of steel rebar corrosion, chloride radical is the most commonly used (Sun, & Niu, 2010).

Chloride ions are the most dangerous (Sun, & Niu, 2010), the transmission of these ions from the protective layer to surface reinforcement destroys the passivation film on renovation liquidates reinforced corrosion.

Due to the effect on the durability and life of the structure the transmission and penetration speed as well as concentration with which ions in the protective layer are directly liable material (Tian, et al., 2023), therefore, like conventional silicate-based concrete.

Therefore, just as concrete is of significance in studying chlorine ion penetration resistance of ordinary silicate materials for the elucidation of rust and crack induced by structure to enhance performance during service life but also geo-

polymerization since considerable policy changes.

Currently, the research of geopolymer materials has become a hot spot (Singh, et al., 2015; Sun, et al., 2023; Lyu, et al., 2023), especially in raw material composition, preparation process and reaction mechanism.

Not only the raw material component, and preparation process but even the reaction mechanism and micro-mechanism of mineral inorganics can be established theoretical model (Yang, et al., 2022; Huang, Kumar, & Dai, 2023; Sudha, et al., 2022; Aravind, Nagajothi, & Elavenil, 2021). GKs have been widely used as a binding material for reconstructing concrete structures instead of cement in recent years, contributing to the progress of research into when geopolymers show resistance against chlorine infiltration. However, such studies were not comprehensive enough and therefore more systematic work on GK properties is needed.

There has been some progress made in the last years, but a systematic summarization is still missing. For this purpose, the current paper is arranged: it summarizes the chloride ion transportation of geopolymer concrete by introducing a new concept on how chloride ions are carried in GPC and its consequence into nitric acid conditions related to CADC; summarizing the penetration retardation mechanism toward chlorides.

Chloride ion permeation resistance of geopolymer concrete based on the chloride ion transport mechanism was introduced, and then testing methods and influence factors were summarized.

Mechanism of Chloride Transport in Geopolymer Concrete

Basic Model

The primary channels by which chloride ions move in GPC take the forms of diffusion, convection, electromigration and also thermal transport. In local systems, this refers to ions diffusing along a chemical potential gradient

from a region of high concentration (IN) to a region of low concentration.

Diffusion is the movement of ions from areas of high concentration to areas of low concentration, driven by a chemical gradient. This process can occur until a steady state is reached, or it can occur in a non-steady-state manner. The number 2. Steady-state diffusion refers to a situation when the Former case occurs.

The expression for diffusion flux (Chen, & Pan, 2016) when the diffusional is steady state diffusion can be written by equation (1).

$$J_i = -D_i * \left(\frac{dc}{dx}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where: J_i is the diffusive flux, mol/ (m².s); D_i is the diffusion coefficient, m² / s; C is the chloride concentration, mol/m³; x is the position variable, m. The following table shows the diffusive fluxes and the diffusion coefficients.

The chloride ion transport in real engineering is mostly unsteady diffusion, i.e., it varies with time also known as convection phenomena and expression of the unsteady-state convection-reaction-diffusion equation can be derived from Eq (2).

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -D * \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

Where: D is the non-steady state diffusion coefficient of chloride ions, m²/s; t is the migration time, s. The migration time of chloride ions refers to the duration it takes for the chloride ions to migrate.

The essence of electromigration is the process where a group of charged ions flow from low potential to high under effective driving force by an electric field. The chloride ion migration test for subtoxic Brianna solution corrosion is accelerated and the transmigration process is illustrated in Fig 1.

Figure 1. Illustrates the Migration Process of Accelerated Chloride Ions During a Migration Test

Source: Shi, C. J., Deng, D. H., & Xie, Y. J. (2006)

The specimen gets heated during the presence of high applied voltage and transfers a great amount of heat, finally resulting in dissolving into metal at the positive electrode chamber and then oxidizing to get deposited at the negative electrode chamber. The equation for the electromigration flux of negative chloride ions due to an applied electric field is provided in Eq. 3 below:

$$J_N = -D_i * C * \frac{\lambda F \Delta \Psi}{RTa} \quad (3)$$

Where: J_N is the electromigration flux, mol/ (m².s); λ is the charge of the charged ions; F is Faraday's constant; R is the molar gas constant; T_a is the absolute temperature, K; Ψ is the electric potential, V. The electric potential of the charged ions is the electric force, V.

In the context of geopolymers concrete, it was expected that a high-temperature environment would accelerate the migration of ions (Shi, Deng, & Xie, 2006). This was found to be true for chloride ions in two scenarios: (1) when the initial concentration was uniform, and (2) when a heated part caused Cl⁻ ions to migrate from hotter regions to cooler regions.; e.g., exposed de-iced saline surface painted with salt-saturated water having pore solution adequately migrate

throughout fresher side. (EIF), finally one can conclude higher temperature samples present an enhanced rate compared to lower temperature samples as all depend on D or q values at each stage: diffusivity over potential without effect due to solubility constant may alter the same trend (Fu, Zhang, & Niu, 2023). Equation (4) expresses the relationship between diffusion coefficient D and temperature T.

$$D(T) = A * \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

Where: A is a constant and E_a is the apparent activation energy required for chloride ion diffusion.

Convection is the migration of ions in the concrete pore solution due to density changes caused by concentration differences or temperature differences. Convection flow through the cross-section of the unit time is calculated as shown in equation (5).

$$J_c = C_v \quad (5)$$

Revised Model

Chloride penetration of concrete structures in actual service environments was a complex and multifactorial process, modulated by multiple factors (Sun, & Niu, 2010), so the modification models for chloride transport of geopolymers concrete focused on couplings between different factors (Huang, Kumar, & Dai, 2023).

Notably, aluminium Al content is a factor that could change the gel structure of the concrete, and when its content is high, it could inhibit the chloride ion transport. Accordingly, in the study of chloride ion transport characteristics of fly ash geopolymers concrete FAGPC, Fu et al. (2023) developed a chloride ion transport model considering the combined effect of bound chloride ions, loading, porosity, as well as convection, as presented in Eq 6.

$$C(x, t) = C_s * \left(1 - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{\left(4 * \left(\frac{\varphi D_i}{\tau^2(\varphi + (1-\varphi)\rho_c)}\right) ** G(\varepsilon, i) * R_f t\right)}}\right)\right) \quad (6)$$

Where: C_s —Surface chloride content, % (mass fraction); φ —Porosity of FAGPC; τ —Pore curvature; $D_i = 2.03 \times 10^{-9}$ m/s is the diffusion coefficient of chloride ions; $\rho_c = 2200$ kg/m³ is the density of FAG PC material (age name); K—Fitting Coefficient; $G(\varepsilon, i)$ —Relationship between damage factor $G(\varepsilon, i)$ and strain damage variable ε ; R_f —Water replacement coefficient.

Turgeon et al. (2023) used a 2D multi-ion transport model, named Trans Chlor-2UD, to simulate the chloride ingress in cracked UHPC beams and established an Equation (7) with consideration of water migration/multi-ion diffusion/coupled temperature/electric field/ionic force as follows

$$\frac{\partial(wC_i)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (wD_1^E \cdot \nabla(C_i)) + \frac{wD_1^E \cdot Fz_i}{RT} \Delta(\Psi)C_i + wD_1^E \cdot C_i \cdot \Delta(\ln \gamma_i) \quad (7)$$

Where: C_i is the ion concentration, mol / L; w is the water content per volume of concrete, m³ / m³; D_1^E is the ion diff. coefficient, m² / s; z_i is the number of valence electrons of ions; F is Faraday's constant; Ψ is the electric potential, V; R is the ideal gas constant; T is the temperature, K; γ_i is the chemical activity coefficient.

Based on Fick's second law and the law of conservation of mass, Li Yuhang et al [23] established the chloride ion permeation model of lithium slag concrete under continuous loading, as shown in (8) and (9).

$$\frac{dc_f}{dt} = \frac{\partial[\operatorname{Div} \cdot \operatorname{grad}(c_f)]}{\partial x} + k \left(C_b - \frac{\alpha c_f}{(1 + \beta c_f)} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$k = k_a k_b k_c \quad (9)$$

where D_i is the chloride diffusion coefficient, C_f is the free chloride content, C_b is the bound chloride content, $\text{grad}(C_f)$ is the free chloride gradient, x is the depth, t is the time, k is the integrated deterioration effect coefficient, k_a is the environmental influence coefficient, k_b is the load influence coefficient, k_c is the material influence coefficient, α , β - Langmuir adsorption parameters for concrete.

Li Yuhang et al (2023) corrected the coefficient of α based on the Langmuir model by considering the effect of compressive stress on the electric flux:

$$C_b = \frac{\alpha C_f}{(1 + 4.0 C_f)} \quad (10)$$

Where: $\alpha = \lambda (-15.5b^2 + 1.8b + 11.8)$ ($0 \leq b \leq 0.3$, $0.5 \leq \lambda \leq 2$), b is the amount of lithium residue substitution, λ is the correction factor.

Currently, the Study on the anti-chlorine permeation performance of geopolymers is focused on the micro-mechanism level such as the evaluation chloride transport performance of geopolymers under different test methods (Zhang, Fang, & Shen, 2022; Wei, et al., 2022; Wang, et al., 2023), study pore structures for concrete in diverse environmental conditions and effect type optimal amount admixture to anti-chlorine / chemical resistance property for fresh mixture reactive powder mixtures (Li, et al., 2022). The chloride ion permeation mechanism and modelling of this kind of single factor is less in current literature data, whereas it exhibits practical significance in its application under the corresponding mechanism including high temperature, freeze-thaw or other environmental conditions. Proceeding to the necessity for deep investigation concerning geopolymer concrete resistance towards chloride ion.

Procedure for Evaluating the Resistance of Geopolymer Concrete to the Penetration of Chloride Ions

The evaluation of geopolymer concrete's ability to resist the penetration of chloride ions mostly involves long-term exposure testing and chloride ion electron acceleration tests. A long-term exposure test is conducted to subject the concrete specimen to a chloride salt environment for an extended duration to examine the impact of chloride ions on the specimen. However, the test period is lengthy and there are numerous influencing factors and environmental variations, which pose challenges in drawing general conclusions (Okoye, Prakash, & Singh, 2017; Çevik, et al., 2018; Babae, & Castel, 2016). Among the chloride ion electron acceleration methods, the rapid chloride ion permeability test (RCPT) and rapid chloride ions migration (RCM) are the more common methods for the resistance to chloride ion permeation test, and the test devices of RCPT and RCM are shown in Figure 2. The test setup of RCPT and RCM is shown in Fig. 2. The principle of RCPT is to accelerate the movement of chloride ions through the action of an applied electric field and to record the voltage flowing through the test at regular intervals. The quantification and evaluation of concrete's resistance to chloride penetration is conducted using the ASTM C 1202 (Lee, Wang, & Ding, 2019) standard.

The RCPT testing method measures the chloride penetration resistance of concrete by determining the conductivity under a direct current field, which is convenient to control with a short test with rapidity and good repeatability characteristics; however, due to structure limitation, its measurement value is not accurate enough to accurately describe real chloride penetration ability rupture given in reference (Jiang, & 2004). The principle of the RCM is to apply a direct current (DC) external electric field on concrete slabs to induce and attract chloride ions into specimens, then separate them from the solution by distractive process and finally stain their precipitate with AgNO_3 visualized in deep penetration depth. The depth of

penetration of chloride ions in concrete is determined by the AgNO_3 colourimetric method, and at last calculation, resistance to chloride ion permeability can be computed through the Nernst - Planck equation.

The Nernst-Planck equation, as given in equation (11), is used to compute the unstable diffusion coefficient of chloride ions.

$$D_M = \frac{0.0239 \cdot (273 + T)}{(U - 2)t} (X_d - 0.0238) \times \sqrt{\frac{(273 + T)dX_d}{(U - 2)}} \quad (11)$$

Where: D_M is the diffusion coefficient of chloride ions, m^2 / s ; U is the voltage value, V ; T is the average temperature of the solution, K ; d is the thickness of concrete specimen, m ; t is the duration of energization, s ; X_d is the average value of the depth of penetration of chloride ions measured by AgNO_3 colourimetric method,

m . The RCM test method can precisely determine the depth of chloride ion penetration in concrete under an applied electric field because it uses ideal experimental apparatus and standards.

The RCM test method is characterised by its excellent experimental equipment and standards, ease of operation, and ability to accurately determine the diffusion coefficient of chloride ions under the influence of an applied electric field. However, when using the AgNO_3 colorimetric method to measure the depth of chloride ion penetration in concrete, a reaction occurs between AgNO_3 and chloride ions as well as hydroxide ions in the pore solution. This reaction produces white AgCl and dark brown A . When the concentration of chloride ions relative to hydroxide ions is more than 4, the reaction mixture exhibits a brown colouration, which hinders the clear identification of its discolouration boundaries (Yang, & Su, 2002; He, et al., 2019; Fang, Wang, & Luo, 2018; Zeng, et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Displays a Schematic Diagram Illustrating the Experimental Setup for the RCPT and RCM Technique

Source: Jiang, L. H., & Li, J. (2004), Yang, C. C., & Su, J. K. (2002)

Fang Zheng et al (2018) used an electroosmotic pulse test to investigate the ionic attack resistance of concrete based on the principle of the electroosmotic pulse.

Fang Zheng et al. (2018) explored the ion erosion resistance of concrete by an electroosmotic pulse (EOP) based on the principle of electroosmosis and found that better ion

migration characteristics can be obtained by EOP than simple electroosmosis.

It was found that better ionic migration characteristics could be obtained by using EOP than simple electroosmosis. To solve the problem of real-time and in-situ monitoring of concrete permeability, Wang Chong et al. (2023)

proposed a DC-order transient resistivity method to determine the resistivity of concrete and analysed the impact of different factors like mineral admixtures, water-cement ratio, water saturation of concrete and ambient temperature on the transient resistivity of concrete, and the transient resistivity tester is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Transient Resistance Tester
Source: Zeng, T., Fang, Z., Xiong, G. Q., et al. (2023)

Nybo et al. (2019) examined the impact of several parameters on the temporary resistance of concrete using the nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) pulsed gradient spin echo technique (PGSE).

Nybo et al. (2019) measured the electroosmotic flow (EOF) and ionic dispersion of concrete based on the nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and pulsed gradient spin echo (PGSE) technique, and the changes in the pore structure of the concrete might be measured at a finer

scale by PGSE. The non-contact resistivity (NC-ER) (Chen, 2021) is also one of the rapid test methods with an applied electric field, but the difference is that it uses alternating current and does not require contact between the specimen and the electrodes, thus eliminating the effect of electrode reaction (Xiao, et al., 2016) and making the test results more accurate. Table 1 summarizes the chloride penetration test methods and their applicability.

Table 1. Chloride Ion Penetration Test Method and Its Applicability

Test Method	Specificity	Limitation	Reference
RCPT	Simple control, short test time, good repeatability	Limited accuracy of measurement results	Jiang, L. H., & Li, J. (2004)
RCM	perfect experimental equipment and standards, easy to operate, and can accurately calculate the diffusion coefficient of cl ⁻ ions.	The brown colour of the reaction mixture makes it difficult to distinguish its discolouration borders.	Yang, C. C., & Su, J. K. (2002); He, R., Ye, H. L., Ma, H. Y., et al. (2019)
EOP	Better ion mobility characteristics can be obtained	Inability to address real-time, in situ monitoring.	Fang, Z., Wang, C., & Luo, Y. L. (2018)

DC Order Transient Resistance Method	The effect of different factors on the electrical resistivity of concrete can be analyzed.		Zeng, T., Fang, Z., Xiong, G. Q., et al. (2023)
PGSE	Enables measurement of changes in finer pore structures.		Nybo, E., Maier, R. S., Lauchnor, E. G., et al. (2019)
NC-ER	No contact between specimen and electrode required		Chen, J. W. (2021)
ACMT	Realistic simulation of steady-state and unsteady-state migration of Cl^- ions in concrete	Difficulty in data collection, lack of relevant test equipment, and test standards	He, F. Q., Shi, C. J., Yuan, Q., et al. (2011); Maes, M., Gruyaert, E., & De Belie, N. (2013)
NEL	Suitable for evaluating the chloride permeability of high-performance concrete.	Test results are conservative and not suitable for life prediction	Yang, C. C., & Wang, L. C. (2004); Chiang, C. T., & Yang, C. C. (2007)
Permit	Fast test speed and easy data collection	Limited scope of application, not suitable for concrete containing mineral admixtures.	Xue, J. P., Lin, Y. J., Chen, J. K., et al. (2018); Luo, B. G., & Qin, H. Y. (2014)
EIS	Considers the influence of time, environment, material microstructure, and other factors, leading to more accurate results.	Currently, in the laboratory stage, many questions remain to be investigated.	Yan, P. Y., Yang, J. B., & Wu, Z. G. (2008); Cabeza, M., Keddad, M., Nóvoa, X. R., et al. (2006)

Note: ACMT: Represents Accelerated Chloride Migration Test. NEL: Represents Nernst Einstein Lab Method. EIS: Represents Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy.

Variables Influencing the Resistance of Geopolymer Concrete to the Infiltration of Chloride Ions

Exciter

Factors affecting the performance of exciter on the resistivity of geopolymer concrete against chloride penetration. mainly include the type and concentration of the exciter. Chindaprasirt et al. (2014) showed that when the Level of sodium hydroxide was increased, the permeability of chloride ions in fly ash GPC was significantly reduced, and similar results were obtained in tests on geopolymer concrete specimens using the rapid chloride migration coefficient method by Sadangi et al. A similar conclusion was reached by Sadangi et al. (2022). This suggests that the alkalizing agent concentration does affect the resistance of geopolymers to chloride permeation. It was found in Chen, Q. (2008) that when sodium hydroxide and water glass were used as alkalizing agents, the chloride diffusion

of alkali slag concrete was improved, and its flux was significantly smaller than that of geopolymer concrete alkalized with water glass, and the chloride permeability was decreased dramatically with the increase of the concentration of both alkalizing agents. Sodium hydroxide-excited geopolymer concrete has a high resistance to chloride permeation Yu, Q., Wan, X. M., Zhao, T. J., et al. (2022) because water glass-excited slag geopolymer concrete produces more initial cracks (Melo, Cincotto, & Repette, 2008; Ryu, et al., 2013; Liu, 2015), which provide more channels for chloride ion transport, thus reducing its resistance to chloride permeation. Liu Xiaojin (2015) through the study of water glass-excited alkali slag geopolymer concrete pore solution conductivity changes with age, found that water glass-excited geopolymer concrete pore solution conductivity decreases with age, which is due to a rise in pore space, the movement of Cl^- ions in the pore space is restricted, the solution conductivity is also

reduced, water glass-excited alkali slag geopolymer concrete pore solution conductivity changes with age as shown in Figure 4. The change of water glass excited alkali slag geopolymer concrete pore solution electrical conductivity with age is shown in Fig. 4 (M_s is the modulus of water glass).

Figure 4. Variation of Conductivity of Alkali Slag Geopolymer

As can be seen in Figure 4, with the growth of age, the solution conductivity is also reduced, so the system conductivity is also reduced. Although the porosity of water-glass-excited concrete is higher than that of sodium hydroxide, the effect of the two pores on the transport is small (Liu, 2015; Zhang, 2018). A high concentration of alkali exciter and a suitable type of alkali exciter will promote the leaching of silicon and aluminium elements in the geopolymer and produce a stronger geopolymerization reaction, which results in more chlorides, denser pores within the matrix, and increased resistance to Cl-ion penetration.

The pore space within the matrix becomes denser and the resistance to chloride ion permeation is increased.

Alkali Dosage and Water Glass Modulus

The permeability properties of geopolymer materials are influenced by the alkali dosage and water glass modulus when water glass is utilised as an exciter (Wang, Scrivener, & Pratt, 1994). Ma et al. (2016) showed that the Cl⁻-diffusion coefficient of geopolymer concrete decreases

with the rising of alkali dosing, and the effect of alkali dosing on the non-stationary diffusion coefficient of alkali-excited slag concrete is shown in Fig. 5. With the increase of alkali dosage, the hydration degree of slag also increases accordingly, which produces more hydration products, and the hydration products combine with free chloride ions or sodium ions to reduce the porosity of geopolymer concrete, which leads to the decrease of its non-steady state coefficient.

Figure 5. Effect of Alkali Admixture Dosage on Unsteady State

According to Du Tianling et al. (2021), the strength of geopolymer concrete increases and then decreases with the increase of water glass modulus. Through micro-mechanism analysis, when the alkali dosage is certain, the silica ions in water glass will undergo a chemical reaction with calcium ions to generate hydrated calcium silicate, and at the same time, the chloride ions and silica ions in the geopolymer concrete will gather near the calcium silicate to further polymerization, which will form a denser mesh structure, and improve the resistance to chloride penetration of the geopolymer system. Ma et al. (2016) found through experimental research that when the alkali doping is certain, the rise of the water glass modulus can enhance the alkali activation effect, thus reducing the chloride permeability of the system. The impact of water glass modulus M_s on the non-stationary diffusion coefficient D_{nssd} of geopolymer concrete is shown in Fig. 6, and the non-

stationary diffusion coefficient is the smallest when the water glass modulus is 1.5.

Figure 6. Effect of Water Glass Modulus on Unsteady State

When the alkali exciter is water glass, the electrical flux of geopolymer concrete increases with increasing alkali admixture (Du, 2021). This is because the increase in alkali dosage leads to an increase in the metal ion content within the geopolymer, which leads to an error in the measurement of the chloride ion content in the pores using the electrical flux method.

Type of Admixture

Depending on the number of admixtures, they are classified as single or double admixtures. Bernal et al. (2012) obtained that the chloride diffusion coefficient of alkali slag geopolymer concrete mixed with 20% (mole fraction) of metakaolin (MK) was the lowest when the alkalizing agent to precursor molar ratio was 3.6. Jumaa et al. (2022) observed that the chloride diffusion coefficient of alkali slag in geopolymer concrete mixed with nano clay (NC) and nano titanium (NT) was the lowest when the alkaline agent was 3.6% (mole fraction). Jumaa et al. [60] investigated the collective application of nano clay (NC) and nano titanium (NT) in

geopolymer and obtained that fly ash geopolymer concrete mixed with 1% (mass fraction) NC and 1.25% (mass fraction) NT had better chlorine ion permeation resistance, which was attributed to the volcanic ash reaction of the nanomaterials that lowered the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) among the slurry and aggregates, and the chloride diffusion coefficient of alkali slag geopolymer concrete was the lowest. Yavana et al. (2022) Obtained that the drying shrinkage of geopolymer concrete could be minimized and the chloride penetration resistance of geopolymer concrete could be improved by mixing polypropylene fibre (PPF) alone in FAGPC. Jayanthi et al. (2023) found that microfine biomass silica (MBS) alone in granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS) had the best resistance to chloride penetration when mixed with 20% (mass fraction) MBS. Alawi et al. (2022) made rubber geopolymer concrete (RGPC) by mixing 1.0% (v/v) of waste rubber fibres in geopolymer and then mixed 5% (v/v) of steel fibres and 1% (v/v) of silica and found that RGPC had better properties of resistance to chloride ion penetration. Babu et al. (2023) found that the optimum anti-chlorine permeation mixing ratio of mixed geopolymers $m(FA): m(GGBS): m(MK) = 50:30:20$. Mousavinejad et al. (2021) found that by mixing steel fibre and polypropylene fibre (PPF) with high-performance geopolymer concretes prepared from ground blast furnace slag and silica fume, it was possible to achieve the same result with the addition of steel fibre and polypropylene fibre. The results showed that the addition of zeolite enhanced the geopolymer process and formed a stable zeolite structure, while bentonite played the role of filler to make the geopolymer structure more compact and stable, and the geopolymer structure was more stable. and bentonite acts as a filler to prepare the geopolymer structure denser. Table 2 shows the optimum mixing levels of geopolymer concrete admixtures, and the chlorine permeability of the concrete in the table is better than that of OPC concrete.

Table 2. Optimum Content of Geopolymer concrete Admixtures

Tables Geopolymer type	Tables Admixture type	Tables Optimum dosage	Tables Reaction product	Tables Resistance compared to OPC	Tables Ref.
Alkali slag geopolymer	MK	20% (mole fraction)		Better	Bernal, S. A., Mejía de Gutiérrez, R., & Provis, J. L. (2012)
Fly ash geopolymer	NC, NT	1% (mass fraction) 1.25% (mass fraction).	Silicate compounds	Better	Jumaa, N. H., Ali, I. M., Nasr, M. S., et al. (2022)
Fly ash geopolymer	PPF	0.6% (mass fraction)		Better	Yavana, R. S., Saleh, N. M., & Bin, N. J. (2022)
Blast furnace slag geopolymer	MBS	20% (mass fraction)	C-S-H gel	Better	Yavana, R. S., Saleh, N. M., & Bin, N. J. (2022)
Rubber geopolymer	SF, SiO ₂	5% (mass fraction), 1% (mass fraction)		Better	Jayanthi, V., Avudaiappan, S., Amran, M., et al. (2023)
Fly ash geopolymer	GGBS, MK	30% (mass fraction), 20% (mass fraction)		Better	Alawi Al-Sodani, K. A. (2022)
Blast furnace slag, silica fume geopolymer	SF, PPF	1.75% (volume fraction). 0.25% (volume fraction).		Better	Babu, G. K., Rao, K. V., & Dey, S. (2023)
Fly ash geopolymer	Zeolite, bentonite		Zeolite structure	Better	Mousavinejad, S. H. G., & Sammak, M. (2021)

For porous media materials such as concrete, the nature of chloride ion penetration is the spread of ions in the pore solution, as long as there is a concentration difference in the outside world, the ions will inevitably penetrate from the outside of the material to the inside of the material, thus affecting its structural properties. Studies (Hu, Zhu, & Long, 2009) have found that incorporating reactive mineral materials for instance slag and fly ash into concrete can effectively enhance the resistance of concrete to chloride permeation. The primary reason for this is that an appropriate amount of admixtures can be regarded as a certain type of calcium silicate-rich precursors added to the geopolymer system, which contributes more generation of gel (N - A - S - H) and accelerates C3S (C-A-S-H) and N-A-S-(H)-CaHS coexisted in it due to stable hydration environment provided by alumina-activated slag reacted with alkaline activators. This results much denser pore structure contributing to improvement in microstructure characteristics about HK diffusing through matrix compared with OPC concrete. The

microstructural density of geopolymer concrete was increased by means allowing, Ultimately the resistance to chloride ion penetration in it, would get enhanced way. Furthermore, the higher fineness of metakaolin and nanomaterials may enhance the density of concrete's microstructure enabling it as an applicative option for reducing porosity leading to improving chloride ion permeation resistance in geopolymer concrete.

Hence enhances penetration resistance to the chloride ions (Huseien, et al., 2018; Prabu, Shalini, & Kumar, 2014). The fibres would act as a bridging effect in case of cracks; thus, inhibiting or minimizing the crack dilation with an intact and connected geopolymer matrix.

For the bitumen foams, when fibres are incorporated with them and then used in geopolymer concrete; due to the bridging effect of these cracks by fibres that exist between cracked-part i.e., fibre surface-cracked part interface helps inhibition or reduction of crack growth (and therefore closing) which eventually

influence on chloride penetration (Farhan, Johari, & Demirboğa, 2021).

Conclusion and Perspective

The durability study and practical engineering application of geopolymer concrete greatly depend on its capacity to resist the absorption of anti-chlorine ions. This work is an introduction to the process by which chloride ions are transported in geopolymer concrete.

This study presents an overview of the chloride ion transport process in geopolymer concrete. It summarises the test method for evaluating the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion permeation, along with the elements that influence this resistance. The paper concludes with the following findings.

The following conclusions are drawn:

(1) The test technique used to evaluate the anti-chlorine ion permeation performance of geopolymer concrete is the rapid chloride ion migration coefficient method, which is widely used and known for its excellent precision. The method of determining the coefficient of fast chloride ion movement is widely used and provides more precise results.

(2) The chlorine penetration resistance of geopolymer concrete is influenced by several elements, including the exciter type, alkali dosage, water glass modulus, and admixture type.

The factors affecting the resistance of geopolymer concrete to chloride ion penetration include High concentrations of alkali excitors, suitable alkali exciter types of admixtures that can enhance the geo-polymerization reaction and the resistance to chloride ion penetration.

Since the research on the chlorine ion permeation resistance of geopolymer concrete started relatively late, the choice of research methods and environmental conditions varied among different researchers, resulting in different results. Differences in the choice of research methods and environmental conditions of different researchers resulted in inconsistent

research results. To promote the application of geopolymer concrete in practical projects, the following aspects need to be further studied.

To enhance the usage of geopolymer concrete in real world projects, the following aspects need to be further studied and explored.

(1) The single-factor transmission modelling of the chlorine penetration resistance of geopolymer concrete under high temperature and freeze-thaw environmental conditions is less studied, which can be further investigated in further in-depth study.

(2) The test method of the anti-chlorine ion permeation efficiency of geopolymer concrete is not perfect, and it can be reasonably improved by comparing the chloride ion permeation performance of ordinary concrete with the electromigration test.

To enhance the test procedure for measuring the chloride ion permeability of geopolymer concrete, it is advisable to compare it with the chloride ion permeability of regular concrete and make appropriate enhancements to the electromigration test.

(3) The influence of alkali mixing amount and water glass modulus on the anti-chlorine permeation performance of geopolymer concrete is still controversial and needs further in-depth research.

(4) The accuracy of the colourimetric boundary concentration of chloride ions in geopolymers still needs further study to quantify the chloride ion penetration depth more accurately.

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